

Suitability Evaluation of Pedons from Some Agricultural Communities on the Niger River Flood Plains in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

Achimota A. Dickson

Department of Crop and Soil Science, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Nigeria

Bassey E. Udom

Department of Crop and Soil Science, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Payou T. Ogboin

Department of Crop and Soil Science, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Dickson, A.A., Udom, B.E., & Ogboin, P.T. (2024). Suitability Evaluation of Pedons from Some Agricultural Communities on the Niger River Flood Plains in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 142-151.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).13](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).13)

Abstract:

Farmers under modern agriculture are expected to have direct or indirect knowledge of soil chemical and physical characteristics as well as their suitability for intended uses. This, however, is lacking in Bayelsa State, hence this study examined the potentials and limitations of some lower Niger River plain soils of southern Nigeria and their suitability for maize production. Based on landform differences, landscape segments were separated into three mapping units per location while profile pits were dug in each unit and morphologically described. Horizon differentiation guided soil sample collection followed by laboratory analysis. Silt loam

dominated soil texture while Ca dominated the exchange complex but exchangeable bases concentration was generally low. Organic C, total N and available P concentrations were closely related and low which was attributed to land clearing and frequent bush burning. Excessive rainfall and inadequate length of day were the most limiting factors under climatic factors while temperature and relative humidity were highly suitable. The ELM3 and TFN3 pedons flooded each year by Nun and Forcados Rivers, respectively, were marginally suitable S3f. Texturally, ELM1, ELM2 and TFN1 were highly suitable (S1) while ELM3, TFN2 and TFN3 were moderately suitable (S2). Due to insufficient length of dry days and wetness challenges owing to excessive rainfall, all pedons were placed under actually not suitable but potentially suitable (N1) class. Improvement measures recommended included planting early in the dry spell to avoid excessive wetness and making available more dry days as well as organic matter conservation, avoiding frequent land clearing and bush burning.

Keywords: *Land Suitability, Land Characteristics, Floodplains, Niger River, Bayelsa State.*

Introduction

Soils are pivotal in sustaining life on planet earth. Nearly all of the food that humans consume, except what is harvested from marine environments, is grown in the earth's surface (Schoonover and Crim, 2015). A nation's ability

to advance economically, industrially, and technologically depends, therefore, on having a strong agricultural base. Soil is the foundation for agricultural development and all investments revolve around it (Blum, 2013; Usman and Kundiri, 2016). Soil provides ecosystem services

critical to life e.g., soil acts as a water filter and a growing medium; providing habitat for billions of organisms, contributing to biodiversity; and supplies most of the antibiotics used to fight diseases. Human's use soil as a holding facility for solid waste, filter for wastewater, and foundation for our cities and towns (Dickson, 2018).

Failures of past and current agricultural development programmes in several Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations have been linked to poor attention given to soil. Land degradation resulting from the widespread abuses of the SSA's soils has been recorded, including bad land clearing and development practices for agriculture, the construction of roads, housing, and industrial estates, quarrying and mining, as well as over-grazing (Blum, 2013; Tully et al., 2015). Other reported activities include improper use of chemicals, and blanket fertilizer application without soil testing (Seitzinger et al., 2010; Abdi et al., 2013). World over, the quantity of agricultural land is diminishing, and most part of the land has been degraded as irreversible and has become unsuitable for agricultural production (Verheye, 2008). Poverty globally, is considered a major cause of land degradation and poor natural resource conservation, leading to reduced agricultural productivity. This degradation is often caused by a mismatch between land use and land potential, specifically using marginal lands for agriculture (Quandt et al., 2020).

According to Dickson et al. (2002), "modern agriculture requires that farmers have direct or indirect knowledge of the soil nutrient status and other chemical and physical characteristics as well as the capability of the soils" which can enable farmers to make informed choices. The need to incorporate land suitability evaluation into soil characterization and classification studies prior to crop cultivation and other agricultural land uses therefore, is of paramount importance. According to Esu (2010), "suitability evaluation of land is an inventory that makes data relevant and applicable to an existing land problem".

But increasing population growth and food demand has necessitated expansion of cultivated land. According to Udoh and Ogunule (2012), "maize, as a major source of calories, is not only humans but also for animals in Nigeria as well as other parts of the world and has resulted to more land being opened up for large scale production". But, Esu (2005), emphasized that "one of the strategies to achieve food security with sustainable environment is to study soil resources to details through soil characterization and land evaluation for various land utilization types". However, for the flood plain soils of the lower Niger River, lands have been utilized intensively for different purposes at the detriment of determining suitability/capability thereby resulting in land degradation and imbalanced ecosystem in a landscape (Dickson et al., 2021). This study, therefore, assessed the potentials and limitations of climatic factors and soil properties in the suitability of some selected soils in the lower Niger River flood plain of the humid South-south Nigeria for maize production.

Materials and Methods

The study Area

The study area lies between latitudes 05 22 03.9 and 04 59 08.9 North, and longitudes 006 30 21.1 and 006 06 54.1 East. Topography is gently sloping. Annual rainfall ranges between 2000 and 4500mm spread over 8 to 10 months of each year, and bimodal, peaking at June and September. The area experience a fairly constant temperature peaking at 30 °C and relative humidity averaging 80% all over the state. The natural vegetation is tropical rain forest and the type of land use is majorly arable cultivation with small sizes of maize, cassava, yam, vegetable, oil palm, cocoa and rubber. The parent material is alluvium transported by the Niger River.

Field Work

An area of 500.4 hectares was chosen to represent the farming communities. The major soil types identified followed the soil survey manual/method (Soil Survey Staff, 2014). Soil sampling procedures as prescribed in the USDA

Soil Taxonomy were followed. Based majorly on the land form differentiations of the area and texture, colour, soil depth, gravel content, landscape segments were classified into three mapping units in each location, making a total of six mapping units. A total of six profile pits were dug and described morphologically. Levee crest, levee slope and alluvial soils in the channels of present active rivers were the land forms chosen for this study in each location and soil samples were collected for laboratory analysis.

Laboratory Analysis

Soil sample collection was guided by horizon differentiation and samples were taken to the laboratory were air-dried, crushed and passed through a-2mm sieve and analyzed using standard procedures which were described by Dickson et al (2021).

Suitability Evaluation

Suitability evaluation of the land was done using the conventional method (FAO, 1976). Pedons were placed in suitability classes by matching their characteristics with the established requirement. The final (aggregate) suitability class indicates the most limiting characteristics of the pedons.

Results and Discussion

Physical and Chemical Characteristics of the Soils

The soil texture was dominated by silt followed by either sand or clay. Textural classification indicate that silt loam dominated most of the soils (Table 1 - Appendix), especially ELM 1, ELM2, TFN1, TFN2 and TFN3 while Elemebiri soil was dominated by sandy loam and loamy sand. Silt/clay ratio was high, suggesting that the soils were young and recent.

Calcium was the dominant element in the soil exchange complex followed by magnesium. Generally, the concentration of exchangeable bases was low which Havlin *et al.* (2012) attributed to leaching loss of basic cations and high acidity. The ECEC of the studied soils were below 6 cmol/kg critical level recommended by

Esu (1991) except the C5 horizons of ELM3 and A2p of TFN2, hence, considered low. In as much as the soils occur in an environment of high rainfall, leaching loss of nutrients is expected. However, since the soils are young and recent, it is possible that the alluvial materials from which these soils were formed are inherently low in basic cations.

Low to medium soil organic matter contents were recorded in spite of the dense vegetative cover. This could be attributed to removal of organic materials through frequent bush burning and high organic matter mineralization. The continuous cultivation with little or no fallowing, abandoning land rotation previously practiced to restore soil fertility further aggravated the situation. Total N, generally, was low except in ELM3. As expected, total N in the surface soil layers was higher than the underlying horizons. As total N in these soils is closely related to soil organic matter as reported by Dickson et al (2021), the low total N was attributed to removal of organic materials through frequent bush burning and high organic matter mineralization which was also reported by Alemayehu *et al.* (2014) for Ethiopian soils.

The available P concentration was low to medium, decreasing with increasing depth. Dickson *et al.* (2021) also reported close relationship between soil organic matter and available P which might be reason for the low available P. Furthermore, Havlin, *et al.* (2012), implicated acidic nature of the soils and possible fixation of P by sesquioxides and the low P values could be attributed to this.

Suitability Evaluation of the Pedons for Maize Production

The suitability evaluation of the lands was done using the conventional method (FAO, 1976) where pedons are placed in suitability classes by matching their characteristics (Table 3) with the established requirement (Table 4 and 5). The final (aggregate) suitability classes (Table 6) were dictated by the most limiting characteristics of each pedon. The land characteristics considered included rainfall, mean annual temperature, slope, wetness, drainage, texture and volume of coarse soil materials with depth, fertility, ECEC,

base saturation, organic carbon, etc as contained in the tables.

Under climatic parameters, the most important limitations to maize production are excess annual rainfall and insufficient length of dry season (days) in the sites. Compared to the 150 to 220 days for the highly suitable class (Sys (1985), the length of dry days in the study sites being insufficient (Table 4). Consequently, all the sites were placed in the S2c suitability class. About 850-1250 mm is the highly suitable rainfall range (Table 3) which when compared with the 2500 mm and above recorded in the study sites placed Elemebiri and Trofani locations in the N1 (actually not suitable but potentially suitable) class. The mean temperature and relative humidity of the locations are within the highly suitable categorization, placing all

pedons in the S1 suitability class. The ELM3 on the channel of the presently active Niger River and TFN3 on the channel of the presently active Forcados River are subject to the Niger River annual floods for some period. These pedons (ELM3 and TFN3), therefore, have flooding issues which placed them in the S3f suitability class. When the textural classes of the pedons were evaluated, ELM1, ELM2 and TFN1 were placed in the S1 class while ELM3, TFN2 and TFN3 were placed in the S2 suitability class. The ELM3, TFN2 and TFN3 pedons textural classes were loamy sand, loamy sand and sandy loam, respectively, and were placed in the S2 suitability class. Soils from the three locations are likely to have low moisture retentive capacity. All the pedons from Elemebiri and Trofani had low coarse fragments content and deep profiles which qualified them for the S1 suitability class.

Table 3. Land Use Requirement for Maize Cultivation Modified from Sys (1985)

Land Quality and Classification	100-95 S1	94-85 S2	84-40 S3	39-20 N1	19-0 N2
1 Climate (c)					
Annual rainfall (mm)	850-1250	850-750 1250-1600	750-600 1600-1800	600-500 1800-2000	- >2000
Length of dry season (days)	150-220	130-150	110-130	90-110	-
Mean annual max. temp. (C)	22-26	22-18	>30-36	36-40	>40
Relative humidity (%)	50-80	50-42	42-36	36-30	-
2 Topography (t)					
Slope	0-2 0-4	2-4 4-8	4-8 8-16	8-16 16-30	>30
3 Wetness (w)					
Flooding	F0	F0	F1	F2	F3
Drainage	Good	Moderate	Imperfect	Poor	v. poor
4 Soil physical characteristics					
Texture	SiC, SiCL, CL, SiL	SL, LS, LfS	LcS, fS	-	S
Coarse fragments (%) 0-10cm	<3	3-15	15-35	35-55	
Depth (cm)	75-100	50-75	20-50	-	<20
5 Fertility					
CEC (cmol/kg)	>24	16-24	<16		
Base saturation (%)	>50	35-50	20-35	<20	-
pH	>5.5-7.0	5.5-7.0	5.0-8.0	5.0-8.0	
OC (mg/kg) 0-15cm	>2	1.2-2	0.8-1.2	<0.8	
Av. P (mg/kg ⁻¹)	>22	13-22	7-13	3-7	<3
Total N (mg/kg)	>0.15	0.10-0.15	0.08-0.10	0.04-0.08	<0.04
Extr. K (cmol/kg)	>0.5	0.3-0.5	0.2-0.3	0.1-0.2	<0.1

Note: F0=No flooding; F1=1-2 months seasonal flooding in >10years; F2=not more than 2-3 months flooding in 5years out of 10; F3=2-4 months flooding every year; SiC=silty clay; SiCL=silty clay loam; SiL=silt loam; SL=sandy loam; LS=loamy sand; LfS=loamy fine sand; S=sand (Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork)

Table 4. Land Characteristics of the Soil Mapping Units at 15cm Depth

SMU	ELM1	ELM2	ELM3	TFN1	TFN2	TFN3
Land quality/characteristic						
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500
Length of dry season (days)	120	120	120	120	120	120
Mean annual Temp. (c)	28	28	28	28	28	28
Relative humidity (%)	78	78	78	78	78	78
Topography (t)						
slope (%)	1	2	3	1	2	3
Wetness (w)						
Flooding	f0	F	f1	f0	f0	f1
Drainage	Good	Mod.	Good	Good	Mod.	Poor
Soil physical charact. (s)						
Texture	SiL	SiL	LS	SiL	LS	SL
Coarse frags. (%) 0-10cm	∩	∩	∩	∩	∩	∩
Fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol/kg)	6.65	5.47	3.49	3.5	3.5	5.33
Base saturation (%)	62	69	66	49	49	66
pH-H2O	5.46	5.44	5.52	5.64	6.16	5.74
OC (%)	2.25	1.03	0.84	1.6	1.28	1.2
Av. P (mg/kg)	18	16	15	12	17	15
Total N (%)	0.25	0.09	0.03	0.13	0.06	0.1
Exch. K (cmol/kg)	1.65	0.09	0.45	0.15	0.15	0.46
Exch. Ca (cmol/kg)	1.26	1.95	0.84	0.78	1.83	1.24
Exch. Mg (cmol/kg)	0.64	0.79	0.94	0.42	0.89	0.93
Salinity (ds/m)	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.09	0.01	0
Mg:K ratio	39	21	100	80	80	202

Note: C=climate; t=topography; w=wetness; s=soil physical properties; f=fertility;

Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork

Table 5. Land Characteristics of the Surface 40 cm Depth of Elemebiri and Trofani Pedons

SMU	ELM1	ELM2	ELM3	TFN1	TFN2	TFN3
Land quality/characteristic						
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500
Length of dry season (days)	130	130	130	130	130	130
Mean annual Temp. (c)	28	28	28	28	28	28
Relative humidity (%)	78	78	78	78	78	78
Topography (t)						
slope (%)	1	2	3	1	2	3
Wetness (w)						
Flooding	F0	F0	F1	F0	F0	F1
Drainage	Good	Mod.	Good	Good	Mod.	Poor
Soil physical characteristics. (s)						
Texture	SiL	SiL	LS	SiL	LS	SL
Coarse frags. (%) 0-10cm	∩	∩	∩	∩	∩	∩
Fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol/kg)	4.6	4.02	3.4	4.3	4.62	3.99
Base saturation (%)	55	55	58	54	43	57
pH-H2O	5.62	5.46	6.22	5.76	6.10	5.76
OC (%)	2.0	0.42	0.81	1.03	0.74	0.82
Av. P (mg/kg)	14	14	14	10	14	9

Total N (%)	0.15	0.04	0.04	0.13	0.06	0.07
Exch. K (cmol/kg)	0.91	0.57	0.40	0.35	0.37	0.64
Salinity (ds/m)	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.09	0.01	0
Mg:K ratio	0.01	0.75	1.83	0.77	1.19	1.02

Note: C=climate; t=topography; w=wetness; s=soil physical properties; f=fertility;

Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork

Table 6. Land Suitability Evaluation of the Pedons from Elemebiri and Trofani

SMU	ELM1	ELM2	ELM3	TFN1	TFN2	TFN3
Land quality/characteristic						
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1
Length of dry season (days)	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
Mean annual Temp. (°C)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Relative humidity (%)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Topography (t)						
slope (%)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Wetness (w)						
Flooding	S1	S1	S3	S1	S1	S3
Drainage	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Soil physical charact. (s)						
Texture	S1	S1	S2	S1	S2	S2
Coarse frags. (%) 0-10cm	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Depth (cm)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol/kg)	S3	S3	S3	S3	S3	S3
Base saturation (%)	S1	S1	S1	S2	S2	S1
pH-H ₂ O	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
OC (%)	S1	S3	S3	S2	S2	S2
Av. P (mg/kg)	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
Total N (%)	S1	S3	N1	S2	N1	S3
Exch. K (cmol/kg)	S1	N1	S2	N1	N1	S2
Limiting characteristics	Cf	Cf	Cwf	cf	Cf	Cwf
Aggregate suitability	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1

Note: C=climate; t=topography; w=wetness; s=soil physical properties; f=fertility; N1= presently unsuitable but potentially suitable

Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork

Due to the low cation exchange capacity (ECEC 3.50 – 6.65 cmol/kg) the pedons were placed in the S3+n suitability class. In spite of the low CEC, base saturation of the ELM1, ELM2, ELM3 and TFN3 are above the 50% stated in the conversion table (Table 4 and 5) for the highly suitable category and were placed in the S1 suitability class. The TFN1 and TFN2 had between 35 and 50% base saturation which qualified them to be in the S2+n suitability class. Using pH, all the pedons qualified to be placed in the S1 suitability class while for organic

matter, ELM1 was placed in the S1 suitability class, TFN1, TFN2 and TFN3, in the S2 and ELM2 and ELM3 in the S3 suitability class. When available P was considered, ELM1, ELM2, ELM3, TFN1, TFN2 and TFN3 having available P levels within 13 – 22 mg/kg, were placed in the S1 suitability class. For total nitrogen, ELM was placed in the S1 suitability class, TFN1 in S2 suitability class, ELM2 and TFN3 in S3 suitability class and ELM3 and TFN1 in N1 class. When exchangeable K was used, ELM1, was placed in the S1 suitability

class, ELM2 and TFN3 in S2 suitability class, and ELM2, TFN1 and TFN2 in N1 suitability class.

Conclusion

Taking into consideration the parameters studied and pedons, the limitations were similar and common to most of the pedons which included excessive rainfall, length of dry season, flooding and wetness, low CEC and organic C, low available P, total N and exchangeable K). Due to excessive rainfall, all the pedons were rated N1. All the pedons are therefore classified actually not suitable but potentially suitable. Measures that could be adopted to improve the limitations included early planting in the dry spell to avoid the excessive rainfalls and wetness in each planting year, incorporation of organic and inorganic fertilizers, avoiding bush burning and practices that lead to destruction of topsoil organic materials, accelerating organic matter mineralization and mixed cropping with leguminous crops to increase soil N.

References

- Abdi, O.A., Glover, E.K. & Luukkanen, O. (2013). Causes and Impacts of Land Degradation and Desertification: Case study of the Sudan. *International Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 3, 40-51. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5923/j.ijaf.20130302.03>
- Alemayehu, Y., Gebrekidan, H. & Beyene, S. (2014). Pedological characteristics and classification of soils along landscapes at Abobo, southwestern lowlands of Ethiopia. *Journal of Soil Science and Environmental Management*, 5, 72-82. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JSSEM13.0432>
- Blum, W.E. (2013). Soil and land resources for agricultural production: general trends and future scenarios-a worldwide perspective. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 1, 1-14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-6339\(15\)30026-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-6339(15)30026-5)
- Dickson, A.A., Tate, J. O., Ogboin, T. P., Cameroon, P. O. William, A.P. (2021). Spatial

variability of selected soil properties of the lower Niger River floodplain soils in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Agriculture and Food Science*, 4(3), 14-27. <http://dx.doi.org/10.52589/AJAFS-6RMAXNLV>

- Dickson, A.A., Tate, O.J., Kamalu, O.J. & Ogboin, T.P. (2021). Characterization and Classification of some lower Niger Alluvial Soils in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Bulgarian Journal of Soil Science, Agrochemistry and Ecology*, 55(3-5).
- Dickson, A.A. (2018). *Characterization, Classification and Suitability Evaluation of Agricultural Soils of selected Communities located along various river systems in Bayelsa State, Southern Nigeria*. Ph.D. Thesis Department of Agronomy, North West University Mafikeng Campus, South Africa. 324p.
- Esu, I.E. (1991). *Detailed Survey of NIHORT Farm at Bakare, Kano State, Nigeria*. Institute for Agricultural Research. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria 72p.
- Esu I.E. (2005). Soil characterization and mapping for Food and Sustainable Environment. In *Managing Soil Resources for Food and Sustainable Environment. Proc. 29th Annual Conf. Soil Science Society of Nigeria* 2005. (pp. 9-18).
- Esu, I.E. (2010). *Soil Characterization, Classification and Survey*. HEBN Publishers Plc, Lagos, Nigeria.
- FAO. (1976). *A Frame work for Land Evaluation*. FAO Soils Bull. 32: FAO, Rome, 87p.
- Havlin, J.L, Beaton, J.D. Tisdale, S.L. & Nelson, W.L. (2012). *Soil Fertility and Fertilizers*. Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- Quandt, A., Herrick, J., Peacock, G., Salley, S., Buni, A., Mkalawa, C.C., & Neff, J. (2020). A standardized land capability classification system for land evaluation using mobile phone technology. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 75(5), 579-589. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.2020.00023>
- Schoonover, J.E & Crim, J.F. (2015). An introduction to soil concepts and the role of soils in watershed management. *Journal of Contemporary Water Research & Education*, 15(1), 21-47.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1936-704X.2015.03186.X>

Seitzinger, S.P., Mayorga, E., Bouwman, A.F., Kroeze, C. Beusen, A.H.W., Billen, G., Van Drecht, G., Dumont, E., Fekete, B.M., Garnter, J. Harrison, J., Wisser, D. & Wollheim, W.M. (2010). Global River Nutrient Export. A Scenario Analysis of Past and Future Trends. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 24, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GB003587>

Soil Survey Staff. (2014). *Keys to Soil Taxonomy*. United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, Washington D.C. 12th Edition

Sys, C. (1985). *Land Evaluation*. Ghent, Belgium. State University of Ghent, International Training Centre for Postgraduate Soil Scientists. Algemeen Bestuur van de Ontwikklingsamenwerking.

Tully, K., Sullivan, C., Weil, R. & Sanchez, P. (2015). The State of Soil Degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa: Baselines, Trajectories and Solutions. *Sustainability*, 7, 6523-6552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7066523>

Udoh, B.T. & Ogunkunle, A.O. (2012). Land suitability evaluation for maize cultivation in a humid tropical area of south eastern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, 22(1), 1-10.

Usman, S. & Kunddiri, A.M. (2016). Role of Soil Science: An answer to sustainable crop production for economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Soil Science*, 61, 1-70. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3923/ijss.2016.61.70>

Varheye, W. (2009). *Land evaluation In Land use and Land Cover II*. Belgium: UNESCO-EOLSS, Ghent University Library

Appendix

Table 1. Some Chemical Characteristics of Elemebiri Soils

Horiz.	Depth Cm	pH	Percent		Avail P Mgkg-1	Exchangeable (cmolk ⁻¹)					Percent BS	Available (mg/kg)			
			TN	Org. C		Ca	Mg	K	Acid.	CEC		Fe	Mn	Zn	Cu
ELM1															
Ap	0-8	5.46	0.25	2.25	18	0.74	0.64	1.65	2.5	5.62	61	50	3.05	15.57	3.00
Ap2	8-21	5.62	0.11	2.24	16	1.26	0.59	0.55	1.5	3.99	62	57	2.90	14.28	3.00
B1	21-34	5.77	0.08	1.52	9	0.78	0.43	0.53	2.4	4.2	43	48	1.81	9.61	3.20
B2	34-65	5.73	0.09	1.5	10	0.76	0.49	1.42	2.0	4.74	58	68	1.91	8.47	3.10
C1	65-90	6.55	0.08	1.22	6	0.75	1.22	0.47	1.8	4.31	58	41	1.35	12.94	1.55
C2	90-118	5.72	0.04	0.7	6	1.2	0.10	0.21	1.8	3.39	47	57	1.30	6.70	3.40
C3	118-150	5.85	0.06	0.71	5	1.22	0.16	0.18	2.4	4.04	41	63	1.42	8.48	1.65
C4	150-200+	5.86	0.05	1.07	3	0.71	0.49	0.72	1.4	3.39	59	62	1.57	7.23	3.60
ELM2															
Ap	0-11	5.44	0.09	1.03	16	1.95	0.09	0.43	1.7	4.27	69	41	3.56	11.95	2.30
Ap2	11-19	5.74	0.01	0.21	17	0.80	0.09	0.62	0.9	2.44	63	60	2.50	9.54	3.20
B1	19-32	6.61	0.02	0.26	14	0.80	0.76	0.58	2.1	4.31	52	64	2.39	14.85	3.65
B2	32-42	6.04	0.02	0.16	10	0.85	0.79	0.66	2.7	5.07	52	65	1.69	16.17	2.95
B3	42-57	6.07	0.01	0.11	7	0.84	0.13	0.44	2.3	3.77	47	42	1.80	13.39	1.25
B4	57-88	5.74	0.02	0.12	8	0.90	0.48	0.70	1.5	3.66	65	53	1.94	16.56	4.70
C1	88-106	6.15	0.03	0.16	6	0.63	0.43	0.18	1.7	2.99	51	51	1.72	8.74	2.90
C2	106-190+	6.18	0.03	0.14	7	0.85	0.36	0.26	0.7	2.21	73	55	1.60	8.66	3.00
ELM3															
A	0-18	5.52	0.03	0.84	15	0.73	0.45	0.45	1.2	2.90	66	62	4.25	11.34	1.90
Ap	18-31	7.00	0.06	0.78	18	0.84	0.97	0.58	1.9	4.37	62	42	3.01	6.75	4.80
Ap2	31-44	6.15	0.04	0.82	9	0.72	0.76	0.18	1.2	2.92	65	53	2.22	4.09	2.25
C1	44-68	5.95	0.02	0.53	9	0.72	0.08	0.12	0.5	1.49	76	42	1.80	6.42	3.10
C2	68-81	5.98	0.04	0.56	10	0.56	0.22	0.33	1.0	2.14	59	78	2.41	3.48	250
C3	81-123	5.79	0.07	0.56	6	0.87	0.08	0.27	1.8	3.10	53	53	2.00	9.66	4.95
C4	123-160	5.86	0.05	0.59	7	1.20	0.43	0.52	2.8	5.63	46	91	1.56	17.98	4.20
C5	160-200+	5.31	0.04	0.57	5	1.28	0.74	1.81	2.2	6.11	68	62	1.60	12.72	5.30

Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork

Table 2. Some Chemical Characteristics of Trofani Soils

Horiz.	Depth Cm	pH	Percent		Avail P (mg/kg)	Exchangeable (cmolkg ⁻¹)					Percent BS	Available (mg/kg)			
			TN	Org. C		Ca	Mg	K	Acid.	CEC		Fe	Mn	Zn	Cu
TFN1															
Ap	0-14	5.64	0.13	1.6	12	0.75	0.12	0.15	1.8	2.89	38	54	2.39	5.41	2.80
A	14-31	5.75	0.06	0.45	8	0.78	0.42	0.65	2.1	3.62	53	49	3.42	15.86	2.40
B1	31-55	5.88	0.03	0.24	4	0.78	0.98	0.26	2.3	4.37	47	34	0.58	6.52	3.80
B2	55-140	5.95	0.02	0.21	11	0.75	0.32	0.62	1.9	3.66	48	79	0.86	9.17	5.70
B3	140-150	5.86	0.04	0.68	5	0.56	0.22	0.16	5.4	6.37	15	77	0.49	9.55	3.40
C	150-200+	5.30	0.04	1.04	16	0.77	0.20	0.61	2.0	4.45	37	76	0.63	14.26	2.55
TFN2															
Ap	0-11	6.16	0.06	1.28	17	0.75	0.12	0.15	1.8	2.89	38	45	1.53	6.33	2.60
A2p	11-35	6.15	0.05	0.59	10	1.83	0.89	0.14	3.3	6.21	47	40	0.74	11.84	0.75
B1	35-44	5.98	0.03	0.35	15	1.22	0.32	0.53	2.6	4.75	45	61	0.65	8.79	3.10
B2	44-70	6.80	0.03	0.31	5	0.89	0.40	1.88	1.8	5.04	64	39	0.80	6.43	4.80
C1	70-126	6.40	0.02	0.19	15	0.78	0.66	0.28	1.0	2.79	64	46	0.45	7.90	5.30
C2	126-200+	6.15	0.02	0.21	2	1.83	0.48	0.28	0.8	3.44	77	60	0.34	8.74	2.40
TFN3															
A	0-13	5.74	0.10	1.20	15	1.24	0.93	0.46	1.8	4.52	60	49	3.80	11.34	5.10
Ap1	13-23	5.98	0.06	0.72	10	0.8	0.68	0.51	1.6	3.66	56	55	2.26	7.20	5.30
Ap2	23-38	5.55	0.05	0.55	3	0.75	0.34	0.94	1.7	3.8	55	92	1.20	9.53	4.10
C1	38-52	6.06	0.03	0.30	9	0.74	0.34	0.50	1.4	3.05	54	75	0.92	8.88	3.90
C2	52-69	5.98	0.06	0.68	5	0.95	1.01	0.63	2.0	4.67	57	66	1.29	15.99	2.59
C3	69-83	6.11	0.03	0.32	4	0.78	0.06	0.19	4.6	5.7	19	83	1.21	0.87	3.40
C4	83-200+	5.79	0.01	0.08	10	0.74	0.53	0.88	1.0	3.92	57	30	0.95	18.52	0.85

Source: Dickson, 2018 fieldwork